

While short-term tactics may work, you may not always be able to keep the results. The great thing about long-term way of thinking is that usually the things you earn, you get to keep them for a very long time as well. The overall process in acquiring them may be slow, but it's well worth it.

If you use short-term or long-term strategy you always need to analyze your competitors, for example, if you have educational website such as essaymap, where you can read about how to write an essay or read about [compare and contrast paper topics](#), also there you can find some educational articles about school, college and university!

Do you have the commitment to learn [how to write content](#) that people will link back to? Are you willing to spend hours of your time learning a skill and then effectively using it in order to achieve something? If you are, then I highly recommend starting to think about your work as [long-term](#) production. Make this change today and see what happens.